

IMPLICATIONS OF THE FULL ELECTRONIC PASSPORT ISSUANCE POLICY ON THE DYNAMICS OF PASSPORT SERVICES AT THE BLITAR IMMIGRATION OFFICE

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ABSTRACT

This article is an analysis of the implications of the full electronic passport issuance policy at the Blitar Immigration Office. This policy is nationally implemented and has been implemented in Blitar Immigration Office since 1st February 2025. Implementation of this policy has an impact on the dynamics of passport services at the Blitar Immigration Office, especially related to the quantity of passport applications and PNBP's receipts obtained after the policy is implemented. In the context of current passport services, this policy has correlated with the implementation of other passport service policies, such as changes in PNBP's rates in passport service contained in PP Number 45 of 2024 and the issuance of Pemenkumham Number 19 of 2024 which regulates of Passport. This study uses a qualitative approach with literature study method that analyzed using public policy theory and the concept of policy implementation. The result of the study are expected to be a reference in the evaluation and reformulation of the full electronic passport issuance policy to minimizing potential problem in policy implementation and better policy reformulation in the future.

Keywords: Services, Electronic Passport, Implementation, Policy, Immigration.

INTRODUCTION

Immigration is a state institution with complex duties and functions encompassing public services, law enforcement, national security, and facilitating community development (Edwinarta, 2024:1). One form of public service provided by Immigration is providing passport services for Indonesian citizens (WNI). Passport service regulations are dynamic, reflecting ongoing policy changes.

Since the post-pandemic period, several regulatory changes have occurred, underpinning passport service policies in Indonesia. The initial regulatory change was the issuance of Government Regulation (PP) Number 51 of 2020 concerning the Third

Amendment to Government Regulation Number 31 of 2013 concerning the Implementing Regulations of Law Number 6 of 2011 concerning Immigration. The main point of change in PP Number 51 of 2020 relates to the formulation of a passport policy with a maximum validity of 10 years, replacing the previous regulation, which required passports to have a maximum validity of 5 years.

The issuance of Government Regulation Number 51 of 2020 subsequently resulted in the formulation of Minister of Law and Human Rights Regulation (Permenkumham) Number 18 of 2022 concerning Amendments to Minister of Law and Human Rights Regulation Number 8 of 2014 concerning Ordinary Passports and Travel Documents in Lieu of Passports. This regulation was subsequently updated to Permenkumham Number 19 of 2024, along with the issuance of PP Number 45 of 2024 concerning Types and Tariffs for Non-Tax State Revenue Applicable to the Ministry of Law and Human Rights.

These policy dynamics have direct implications for the passport service process in Indonesia. One such implication is the issuance of Decree of the Acting Director General of Immigration Number IMI-263.01.02 of 2024 concerning the Full Issuance of Electronic Ordinary Passports at Immigration Offices Throughout Indonesia. Implementation of this policy is being carried out in stages at Immigration Offices throughout Indonesia.

The policy implementation began with the full issuance of e-Passports at the Semarang Immigration Office on October 1, 2024. The Central Jakarta Immigration Office then implemented the full e-Passport issuance policy on November 1, 2024. This policy continued with the full issuance of e-Passports at 13 Immigration Offices: the Soekarno-Hatta Immigration Office, the South Jakarta Immigration Office, the West Jakarta Immigration Office, the Bitung Immigration Office, the Medan Immigration Office, the North Jakarta Immigration Office, the Tangerang Immigration Office, the Makassar Immigration Office, the East Jakarta Immigration Office, the Ngurah Rai Immigration Office, the Batam Immigration Office, the Tanjung Priok Immigration Office, and the Surabaya Immigration Office.

The full e-Passport issuance policy will be implemented in stages at Immigration Offices throughout Indonesia, with implementation at Immigration Offices in West Java and Banten Provinces on January 1, 2025; Central Java, East Java, and Yogyakarta Provinces on February 1, 2025; The provinces of Lampung, Bengkulu, Jambi, South Sumatra and West Sumatra on March 1, 2025; the provinces of Bangka Belitung, Riau Islands, Riau, North Sumatra and Aceh on May 1, 2025; the provinces of West Kalimantan and Central Kalimantan on June 1, 2025; the provinces of East Kalimantan and South

Kalimantan on July 1, 2025; the provinces of Bali, West Nusa Tenggara and East Nusa Tenggara on September 1, 2025; the provinces of Maluku, North Maluku, West Sulawesi, North Sulawesi, Central Sulawesi, Southeast Sulawesi, South Sulawesi and Gorontalo on October 1, 2025; and the provinces of Papua and West Papua on November 1, 2025.

Tabel 1. Timeline for the Full Implementation of the Electronic Passport Issuance Policy

2024

No.	Work unit	Implementation Time
1.	Kantor Imigrasi Kelas I Khusus TPI Semarang	01 Oct 2024
2.	Kantor Imigrasi Kelas I Non TPI Jakarta Pusat	01 Nov 2024
3.	Kantor Imigrasi Kelas I Khusus TPI Soekarno-Hatta	01 Des 2024
4.	Kantor Imigrasi Kelas I Khusus TPI Surabaya	
5.	Kantor Imigrasi Kelas I Khusus TPI Medan	
6.	Kantor Imigrasi Kelas I Khusus TPI Batam	
7.	Kantor Imigrasi Kelas I Khusus TPI Makassar	
8.	Kantor Imigrasi Kelas I Khusus TPI Ngurah Rai	
9.	Kantor Imigrasi Kelas I Khusus Non TPI Jakarta Selatan	
10.	Kantor Imigrasi Kelas I Khusus Non TPI Jakarta Barat	
11.	Kantor Imigrasi Kelas I Khusus Non TPI Tangerang	
12.	Kantor Imigrasi Kelas I TPI Tanjung Priok	
13.	Kantor Imigrasi Kelas I TPI Jakarta Timur	
14.	Kantor Imigrasi Kelas I TPI Jakarta Utara	
15.	Kantor Imigrasi Kelas II TPI Bitung	

Tahun 2025

No.	Immigration Office in Province	Implementation Time
1.	Jawa Barat	01 Jan 2025
2.	Banten	
3.	Jawa Tengah	01 Feb 2025
4.	Jawa Timur	
5.	Daerah Istimewa Yogyakarta	
6.	Lampung	01 Mar 2025
7.	Bengkulu	
8.	Jambi	
9.	Sumatera Selatan	
10.	Sumatera Barat	
11.	Bangka Belitung	01 May 2025
12.	Kepulauan Riau	
13.	Riau	
14.	Sumatera Utara	
15.	Aceh	
16.	Kalimantan Barat	01 Jun 2025
17.	Kalimantan Tengah	
18.	Kalimantan Timur	01 Jul 2025

19.	Kalimantan Selatan	
20.	Bali	
21.	Nusa Tenggara Barat	01 Sept 2025
22.	Nusa Tenggara Timur	
23.	Maluku	01 Oct 2025
24.	Maluku Utara	
25.	Sulawesi Barat	
26.	Sulawesi Utara	
27.	Sulawesi Tengah	
28.	Sulawesi Tenggara	
29.	Sulawesi Selatan	
30.	Gorontalo	
31.	Papua	01 Nov 2025
32.	Papua Barat	

(Source: Decree of the Director General of Immigration, processed by the author, 2024)

The policy of fully issuing electronic passports represents an effort to update the existing passport service policy in Indonesia since the implementation of the electronic passport issuance policy at all Immigration Offices throughout Indonesia. In May 2023, the Directorate General of Immigration issued a policy for issuing electronic passports at 52 Immigration Offices across Indonesia. This policy was then updated in October 2023 through Decree of the Director General of Immigration Number IMI-0235.GR.01.01 of 2023 concerning the Issuance of Electronic Passports at all Immigration Offices in Indonesia. This decree allows electronic passports to be issued at 102 Immigration Offices throughout Indonesia. Furthermore, the expansion of electronic passport issuance also includes an increase in the number of Indonesian representatives who can issue electronic passports through embassies or consulates abroad.

The policy of fully issuing electronic passports aligns with the efforts of the Indonesian government, through the Directorate General of Immigration, to strengthen the Indonesian passport, which is determined by at least four main factors: passport security features, the security situation of the issuing country, the behavior of its citizens abroad, and international diplomacy. The use of electronic passports offers the advantage of a higher level of security to minimize the risk of misuse by implementing international standards for travel documents. This is expected to facilitate faster immigration inspections, especially in several countries that have adopted automated passport inspection systems using chip readers in passports.

However, several factors must be considered in implementing the fully issuing electronic passport policy at Immigration Offices throughout Indonesia, one of which is the regulatory framework used in the policy. The concept of policy formulation within the fully issuing electronic passport policy encompasses a series of systems for formulating requests or support as input, managed by public input, resulting in a robust public policy (Nugroho, 2014:161-163). The regulatory framework is based on the Decree of the Acting Head of the Indonesian Immigration Office. The Directorate General of Immigration needs to consider harmonizing other regulations, such as Minister of Law and Human Rights Regulation Number 19 of 2024 and Government Regulation Number 45 of 2024. This alignment is necessary because both regulations still include Ordinary Non-Electronic Passports in their regulations.

This alignment is necessary to avoid misconceptions in the public. In the context of implementing the Passport Non-Tax State Revenue (PNBP) tariff, for example, a policy is needed during the transition period to the full issuance of Electronic Passports. This transitional policy will gradually reduce the availability of Ordinary Non-Electronic Passports until November 1, 2025. This transitional policy could be implemented similarly to the reduction in the issuance of 24-page Ordinary Passports. Furthermore, the Directorate General of Immigration also needs to emphasize the existence of Polycarbonate Electronic Passports, whose issuance is currently limited. Furthermore, the Directorate General of Immigration will issue passports with a new design on August 17, 2025.

The policy of issuing Electronic Passports in full as a public policy requires the ability to anticipate the implications of the policy, including the responsive capabilities of a public policy (Anggara, 2018:55). The government through The Directorate General of Immigration is expected to fully consider all relevant aspects of the e-Passport issuance

policy to minimize potential problems or obstacles in its implementation. The complexity of passport service policies following the implementation of the PNB (Non-Tax State Revenue) policy stipulated in Government Regulation No. 45 of 2024 is the focus of this research. The research question that arises in this research is: What are the dynamics of the PNB Passport policy formulation from an immigration perspective?

This study examines the dynamics of PNB Passport policy formulation from an immigration perspective using public policy theory and the concept of public policy formulation. The research approach employed is a qualitative approach, combined with a literature review method, comparing previous policy formulations. This study utilized informants who are policy practitioners and stakeholders involved in the PNB Passport policy, which is expected to provide input for the analysis of PNB Passport policy from an immigration perspective.

This research is analyzed using public policy theory, which encompasses everything the government does and doesn't do (Romadlon, 2023:22). This is necessary because the government must be able to resolve conflicts within society, sometimes related to resource scarcity, regulate behavior, and protect basic community rights (Agustino, 2023:5). In the context of this research, the policy on the implementation of non-tax state revenue (PNB) for passports was formulated to adapt to the current circumstances and conditions of passport services. Updating this policy is a periodic process to regulate the alignment of non-tax state revenue with innovations or improvements in passport services.

This aligns with the definition of policy, which is a principle or method of action chosen to guide decision-making for the public, who are the objects of policies made by policymakers, with a focus on the public interest (Kurniawan, 2017:17). Therefore, the concept of policy formulation contained in the Passport Non-Tax State Revenue (PNB) implementation policy needs to be examined conceptually. It is a series of formulation systems for requests or support as input, managed, accompanied by public input, resulting in a competent public policy (Nugroho, 2014: 161-163).

The formulation of the Passport Non-Tax State Revenue (PNB) implementation policy is understood as a policy that seeks to align PNB revenues derived from passport services with the policy updates applicable to the passport service process itself. The issuance of Government Regulation Number 45 of 2024 represents an effort to adjust Passport Non-Tax State Revenue (PNB) revenues following the issuance of Minister of Law and Human Rights Regulation (Permenkumham) Number 19 of 2024 concerning the

Second Amendment to Permenkumham Number 8 of 2014 concerning Passports and Travel Documents in Lieu of Passports. This policy formulation is expected to be able to provide adjustments to PNPB revenues originating from passport services with updated passport service policies in accordance with the concept of policy formulation which seeks to provide a system that produces the ability to anticipate the implications of the policy, including the responsive capabilities of a public policy (Anggara, 2018:55).

METHODOLOGY

This research employs a qualitative approach, employing interview and observation techniques as primary data collection tools. This approach is expected to explore the actions and thoughts of informants while simultaneously finding solutions to the problems being analyzed (Harrison, 2016:91-92). A qualitative approach is also understood as naturalistic research that maintains the natural conditions of the research without any manipulation by the researcher, thus not influencing the dynamics occurring within the research object (Sugiyono, 2019:17). Qualitative research seeks to integrate theory and methods within a methodology related to the research implementation, using a combination of these methodologies to produce specific research elements (Amrullah, 2022:12).

The method used in this research is a literature study, which presents data based on literature read or obtained by the researcher, which can include books or articles, to provide information regarding the background of a problem relevant to the research being conducted (Afrizal, 2014:122). The literature study method is a combination of efforts to collect primary and secondary information sources through data classification stages so that data is produced that is summarized from processing or citing references that are interpreted to produce a conclusion on the research (Darmalaksana, 2020:10).

DISCUSSION

Passport services are part of the Immigration Department's duties and functions, encompassing public services, law enforcement, and national security, as well as facilitating the development of public welfare (Suryawan, 2020:59). As a form of public service, the passport service process is subject to policy dynamics that influence the implementation of services provided to the public.

Data Perbandingan Penerbitan Paspor Bulan Januari-April Tahun 2024 dan 2025

Passport Types	Month							
	Jan 2024	Jan 2025	Feb 2024	Feb 2025	Mar 2024	Mar 2025	April 2024	April 2025
Paspor Biasa 5 th	161	863	102	0	161	0	58	0
Paspor Biasa 10 th	2362	156	2044	0	1713	0	1069	0
E-Paspor 5 th	35	1238	21	850	71	587	52	555
E-Paspor 10 th	216	382	225	311	400	236	502	249
Jumlah Penerbitan	2774	2639	2392	1161	2344	823	1681	804
Layanan Percepatan	97	34	87	6	52	25	34	0

(Source: Blitar Immigration Office, processed by the author, 2025)

Comparative Data on Passport PNBP Revenue for January-February 2024 and 2025 (in Rupiah)

Jenis Paspur	Month							
	Jan 2024	Jan 2025	Feb 2024	Feb 2025	Mar 2024	Mar 2025	April 2024	April 2025
Paspor Biasa 5 th	56.350.000	302.050.000	35.700.000	0	56.350.000	0	20.300.000	0
Paspor Biasa 10 th	826.700.000	54.600.000	715.400.000	0	1.113.450.000	0	694.850.000	0
E-Paspor 5 th	22.750.000	804.700.000	13.650.000	552.500.000	46.150.000	381.550.000	33.800.000	360.750.000
E-Paspor 10 th	140.400.000	248.300.000	146.250.000	202.150.000	380.000.000	224.200.000	476.900.000	236.550.000
Layanan Percepatan	97.000.000	34.000.000	87.000.000	6.000.000	52.000.000	25.000.000	34.000.000	0
Total PNBP	1.120.450.000	1.443.650.000	998.000.000	760.650.000	1.647.950.000	630.750.000	1.259.850.000	597.300.000

(Source: Blitar Immigration Office, processed by the author, 2025)

The data states that in the period from January 2025 to April 2025 there was a decrease in the number of passport issuances following the issuance of a full electronic passport issuance policy at the Blitar Immigration Office which was implemented starting February 1, 2025. The number of passport issuances in February 2025 decreased by 57% compared to passport issuances in January 2025 (Month on Month/MoM). When compared to the number of passport issuances in the same month of the previous year

(Year on Year/YoY), the number of passport issuances in February 2025 decreased by 52% compared to passport issuances in February 2024.

The decline in the number of passport issuances also occurred in subsequent months, such as in March 2025, which decreased by 30% compared to February 2025. Applications further decreased by 3% in April 2025 compared to passport issuances in March 2025. A comparison of passport issuances on an annual basis also shows the same trend, namely a 65% decrease in March 2025 compared to March 2024, and a 53% decrease in April 2025 compared to April 2024. Overall, the number of passport issuances in the period February 2025-April 2025 decreased by 57% compared to passport issuances in the same period in 2024.

On the other hand, the policy of fully electronic passport issuance also impacted Non-Tax State Revenue receipts. (PNBP) derived from passport services throughout the period of January 2025 to April 2025. The amount of passport PNBP receipts in February 2025 decreased by 48% compared to passport PNBP receipts in January 2025. Meanwhile, in comparison to the same month in the previous year, passport PNBP receipts in February 2025 decreased by 24% compared to February 2024.

The decline in passport PNBP receipts also occurred between March 2025 and April 2025. In March 2025, passport PNBP receipts decreased by 18% compared to February 2025. Similarly, passport PNBP receipts in April 2025 decreased by 6% compared to March 2025. The comparison of passport PNBP receipts on an annual basis also decreased by 24% in February 2025 compared to February 2024. Then, it decreased by 62% in March 2025 compared to March 2024. Meanwhile, in April 2025, passport PNBP revenue decreased by 53% compared to and April 2024. Overall, passport PNBP revenues from February 2025 to April 2025 decreased by 50% compared to the period from February 2024 to April 2024.

The decrease in the number of passport applications and PNBP revenues, a consequence of the implementation of the full electronic passport issuance policy at the Blitar Immigration Office, was also influenced by several factors, including the low level of public acceptance of the full electronic passport issuance policy implemented at the Blitar Immigration Office. The Blitar Immigration Office essentially carries out several outreach and information dissemination activities, including Immigration Goes to School, Immigration Goes to Campus, radio talk shows, and Immigration Enters Village activities.

However, the level of public acceptance of the full electronic passport issuance policy at the Blitar Immigration Office is still not fully understood by the general public. This is reflected in one in five messages posted on the Blitar Immigration Office's complaint service, which inquired about the availability of quotas for ordinary non-electronic passports, which were replaced by fully electronic passports starting February 1, 2025. Questions about the availability of quotas for ordinary non-electronic passports continued until the end of April 2025, although with less frequency.

Another factor contributing to the decline in passport applications and non-tax state revenue (PNBP) is the income earned by residents in the Blitar Immigration Office's work area, which influences passport applicants' willingness to apply. The Regency/City Minimum Wage (UMK) for Blitar Regency in 2025 was 2,413,974 rupiah, the UMK for Blitar City in 2025 was 2,481,450 rupiah, and the UMK for Tulungagung Regency in 2025 was 2,470,800 rupiah. Compared to the current PNBP passport fee of 650,000 rupiah for a 5-year e-passport and 950,000 rupiah for a 10-year e-passport, this will certainly increase public consideration when applying for a passport.

Some solutions to address this include conducting more intensive outreach activities that reach a broader and more diverse segment of society. The Blitar Immigration Office has strived to increase outreach to the public through outreach activities during the Tulungagung Regency Car Free Day (CFD), which was held for the first time on May 18, 2025. Another solution is to change the implementation of the e-passport issuance policy. Full e-passport issuance is not based on the province, but based on the UMK or UMR owned by each Immigration Office's work area. In this case, the implementation of the full e-passport issuance policy will be categorized based on the UMK, for example, the Blitar Immigration Office will be given leeway to continue issuing ordinary non-electronic passports along with the Kediri Immigration Office which has a uniform UMK in its work area, but its implementation is differentiated from the Surabaya Immigration Office or Malang Immigration Office which have a higher UMK level.

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